

DECENTRALIZING SECURITY: THE ROLE OF STATE POLICING IN CRIME PREVENTION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The topical issue of crime prevention and control has always gained attention from criminology scholars especially when it comes to the role of the policing system in combating crime in the society. This paper explores the viability, adoption and implementation of state policing in Nigeria as a mechanism for enhancing crime prevention and control. The growing concern on decentralizing policing system to effectively manage various security issues across the country calls for the esteemed need of this research. The study employs a theoretical method approach, with detailed examination and interpretation of existing knowledge and research. The study adopted the Routine Activity Theory (RAT) to explain how decentralized policing strategies can enhance guardianship, reduce criminal opportunities, and address local security needs more effectively. This research acknowledged the significant role of state policing in crime prevention and control, drawing global instances from United States (California and Texas), Canada (Ontario and British Columbia), and Australia (New South Wales and Victoria). This paper also identified the major constraints to state policing in Nigeria to include political resistance, funding, capacity building, inter-agency coordination and community trust. The implications of these findings underscore the pressing need to adopt and implement state policing in Nigeria. This can be achieved through enhanced legislative reforms, allocation of sufficient financial resources to the policing system, continuous training and professional development programs, establishment of clear guidelines and communication channels, and adoption of community policing strategies in crime prevention and control in Nigeria.

Keywords: State Policing, Crime, Prevention, Centralized policing, Community policing

Introduction

Crime prevention and control are paramount to the stability and development of any society. In Nigeria, the centralized policing system under the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) has struggled to effectively manage the diverse and complex security challenges across the country's various regions. This has led to increased calls for the establishment of state policing as a more localized and efficient approach to law enforcement. State policing,

where law enforcement agencies operate at the state level, is seen as a potential solution to enhance crime prevention, improve response times, and foster better community relations. Nigeria's current centralized policing system has been in place since the colonial era, with the NPF being the sole agency responsible for maintaining law and order across the country (Alemika, 2013). Despite various reforms and efforts to modernize the NPF, the system has been criticized for its inefficiency, corruption, and inability to effectively address localized security issues (Ezeoha, 2011). The diverse nature of Nigeria, with its numerous ethnic groups, languages, and cultural practices, poses unique challenges that a centralized police force has found difficult to manage.

In recent years, the rising incidence of terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, and communal conflicts has exposed the limitations of the centralized system. According to Okechukwu (2019), the inability of the NPF to adequately respond to these security challenges has eroded public confidence in the police and underscored the need for a more localized approach to law enforcement. State policing is proposed as a viable alternative, where police forces are established and operated by individual state governments, thereby allowing for Proactive strategies that address specific regional security needs. The centralization of the Nigeria Police Force has resulted in a one-size-fits-all approach to policing, which often fails to account for the unique security dynamics of different regions. This has led to significant gaps in crime prevention and control, with many areas experiencing chronic insecurity and inadequate police presence (Alemika & Chukwuma, 2004). The inefficiencies of the centralized system are further compounded by bureaucratic delays, insufficient funding, and a lack of accountability (Nwolise, 2004). As a result, there is an urgent need to explore the adoption of state policing as a solution to these persistent issues. Over the years, various efforts have been made to adopt state policing in Nigeria. Recognizing the need for a comprehensive and coordinated approach to security, the federal government has taken some steps towards establishing state police forces. However, the implementation of state policing in Nigeria has faced several challenges, including political opposition, bureaucratic hurdles, and resource constraints. One of the earliest attempts to adopt state policing in Nigeria was made in 1967, with the establishment of the Federal Special Task Force (FSTF). However, this initial effort was short-lived, and the FSTF was dissolved only a few years later. In 1999, the Federal Government passed the Police Reform Bill, which aimed to establish a state police system. However, the bill was opposed by some states and was not implemented.

In recent times, there has been a renewed push towards the adoption of state policing in Nigeria. The 2014 National Confab, a gathering of all Nigerian stakeholders, recommended the establishment of state and community policing institutions. However, despite this recommendation, the implementation of state policing remains an ongoing debate. State policing could potentially offer a more effective framework for addressing localized crime, but it also presents several challenges, including concerns about funding, coordination between state and federal agencies, and the potential for political misuse of police forces. Thus, the question arises: Can state policing be a viable solution for crime prevention and control in Nigeria?

Study Objective

The main objective of this study is to critically examine the viability, adoption and implementation of state policing in Nigeria as a mechanism for enhancing crime prevention and control. Specifically, the study aims to evaluate the potential benefits and challenges associated with implementing state policing. By analyzing the experiences of other federal systems with state policing and assessing the specific context of Nigeria, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of whether state policing can address the current inefficiencies of the centralized system and improve overall security outcomes. By addressing these areas, the study aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on police reform in Nigeria and provide actionable recommendations for policymakers, law enforcement agencies, and other stakeholders involved in enhancing security and justice in the country.

Conceptual Clarification

State Policing

State policing refers to a decentralized law enforcement system in which individual states or regions operate their own police forces, independent of federal control. This model contrasts with centralized policing, where a single national police force is responsible for maintaining law and order across the entire country. The rationale behind state policing lies in the belief that local authorities are better positioned to understand and address the unique security challenges of their regions (Ogu, 2016). In Nigeria, the debate over state policing has gained momentum due to the perceived inefficiencies of the centralized Nigeria Police Force (NPF). Critics argue that the NPF's one-size-fits-all approach fails to account for the diverse socio-cultural and geographical landscapes of Nigeria, resulting in inadequate crime prevention and response strategies (Alemika & Chukwuma, 2004). State policing, proponents suggest, would allow for more tailored and responsive law enforcement practices, as local police forces would have greater familiarity with the specific needs and issues of their communities.

Crime Prevention

Crime prevention encompasses a variety of strategies and measures designed to reduce the incidence and impact of criminal activities. It involves proactive approaches aimed at addressing the root causes of crime, deterring potential offenders, and enhancing community safety and security. According to Braga, Papachristos & Hureau (2019), effective crime prevention necessitates a comprehensive approach that includes social, environmental, and situational strategies. Social crime prevention addresses underlying societal issues such as poverty, education deficits, and unemployment, which are often correlated with criminal behavior. By improving socio-economic conditions and providing opportunities for vulnerable populations, social crime prevention seeks to reduce the incentives for engaging in criminal activities (Farrington & Welsh, 2020).

Environmental crime prevention modifies physical environments to decrease opportunities for crime. This can involve strategies like enhanced street lighting, urban design that promotes natural surveillance, and the use of security technologies, such as closed-circuit television (CCTV) systems (Cozens, 2020). Situational crime prevention focuses on minimizing immediate opportunities for crime by increasing the perceived risks of apprehension and reducing the potential rewards of criminal acts. Successful crime prevention also hinges on robust community engagement and collaboration among various stakeholders, including law enforcement, community organizations, and the private sector. By involving community members in crime prevention initiatives and fostering a collective sense of responsibility, these strategies can become more sustainable and effective (Skogan & Hartnett, 2020).

Crime Control

Crime control refers to the diverse strategies and practices utilized by law enforcement agencies and the criminal justice system to manage, reduce, and respond to criminal activities. This encompasses various stages of the criminal justice process, including policing, prosecution, adjudication, and corrections (Mazerolle, Antrobus, & Bennett, 2020). The primary goal of crime control is to uphold public order and safety by deterring criminal behavior, apprehending offenders, and administering justice. Policing plays a crucial role in crime control by enforcing laws, maintaining public order, and protecting individuals and property. Effective policing strategies include patrols, community policing, and intelligence-led policing, which leverage data and analysis to identify and address criminal activities. Community policing, in particular, emphasizes the importance of building

partnerships between law enforcement and the community to collaboratively tackle crime and disorder (Skogan, 2020).

The criminal justice system also significantly contributes to crime control through the processes of prosecution, trial, and sentencing. Ensuring that offenders are fairly and efficiently processed through the legal system is vital for maintaining public confidence in the rule of law and acts as a deterrent to potential offenders (Tonry, 2020). Corrections, including incarceration, rehabilitation, and probation, aim to manage offenders and reduce recidivism by addressing the factors contributing to criminal behavior (Cullen & Jonson, 2017). Hence, crime control is geared towards reducing crime and its reoccurrence. Effective crime control necessitates a coordinated approach that integrates law enforcement, the criminal justice system, community involvement, and policy-making. By addressing both immediate and underlying factors contributing to crime, comprehensive crime control strategies can enhance public safety and decrease the prevalence of criminal activities (Mazerolle *et al.*, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Routine Activity Theory (RAT). Routine Activity Theory, proposed by Cohen and Felson (1979), posits that crime occurs when three elements converge: a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the absence of a capable guardian. This theory emphasizes the importance of situational contexts and routine activities in influencing the opportunities for crime. In the context of state policing in Nigeria, Routine Activity Theory provides a valuable lens to analyze how decentralized policing strategies can enhance guardianship, reduce criminal opportunities, and address local security needs more effectively.

Applying Routine Activity Theory to the analysis of state policing in Nigeria reveals how localized law enforcement can significantly impact crime prevention and control. State police forces, being closer to the communities they serve, can enhance the presence of capable guardianship through increased patrols, community policing initiatives, and better understanding of local crime patterns (Eck & Weisburd, 2015). For instance, areas with high rates of burglary and theft can benefit from targeted interventions that disrupt the routine activities of potential offenders by increasing the perceived risk of apprehension. Additionally, state policing can facilitate quicker responses to incidents, thereby reducing the window of opportunity for criminals. Recent studies highlight that community-oriented policing, a key aspect of state policing, strengthens the relationship between law enforcement and residents, fostering a collaborative environment that enhances informal social controls and community vigilance (Gill, Weisburd, Telep, Vitter, & Bennett, 2014).

Furthermore, state policing can tailor crime prevention strategies to address the specific socioeconomic and cultural contexts of different regions. This localized approach can identify suitable targets and protect them more effectively by implementing context-specific measures such as improved lighting in high-crime areas, community watch programs, and the use of technology like CCTV systems (Braga, Papachristos, & Hureau, 2019). By understanding and integrating the unique routine activities of each community, state policing can reduce the opportunities for crime and enhance overall public safety. Thus, Routine Activity Theory underscores the importance of a decentralized policing model in creating a more adaptive and responsive law enforcement framework in Nigeria.

Methodology

This research explored the concept of state policing in Nigeria, analyzed its potential effectiveness in crime prevention and control, and advocated for its implementation. This paper adopted an explorative design where literature from journals, internet sources, books, reports, newspapers, and magazines were reviewed. Routine Activity Theory was used to underpin the study. The review was done to capture the main thrust of the study. The study synthesized findings from the literature reviewed and contextual analysis to draw conclusions about the adoption and implementation of state policing in Nigeria. This synthesis focused on identifying best practices,

potential challenges, and recommendations for effective implementation of state policing as a viable alternative to centralized policing. Qualitative method was used to interpret data from secondary sources. This involved identifying recurring themes and patterns related to state policing and its implications for crime prevention and control. By leveraging secondary data from journals, internet sources, books, reports, newspapers, magazines, and theoretical frameworks, this methodology contributed to the ongoing discourse on policing in Nigeria and advocate for the adoption of state policing models tailored to the country's diverse security landscape.

Role of State Policing in Crime Prevention and Control

State policing plays a significant role in enhancing crime prevention and control by fostering a localized and context-specific approach to law enforcement. Unlike centralized policing systems, state police forces are inherently more attuned to the unique socio-economic, cultural, and environmental dynamics of their respective regions. This proximity enables state police to implement tailored strategies that can effectively address the specific crime patterns and security needs of local communities. For example, state policing can enhance the presence of capable guardianship through community policing initiatives, which involve regular patrols, community engagement, and the establishment of strong relationships with residents (Gill, Weisburd, Telep, Vitter, & Bennett, 2014). By building trust and cooperation with the community, state police can foster a collaborative environment where informal social controls are strengthened, leading to a more vigilant and cohesive society that actively participates in crime prevention efforts.

Moreover, state policing facilitates quicker and more efficient responses to criminal activities, thereby reducing the opportunities for crime. Routine Activity Theory highlights the importance of disrupting the convergence of motivated offenders, suitable targets, and the absence of capable guardians (Cohen & Felson, 1979). State police, with their localized knowledge and presence, are better positioned to implement situational crime prevention measures such as improving lighting in high-crime areas, organizing community watch programs, and utilizing technology like CCTV systems to monitor and deter criminal behavior (Braga, Papachristos, & Hureau, 2019). These strategies not only increase the perceived risks for potential offenders but also provide a sense of security and protection for community members. By addressing both immediate and underlying factors contributing to crime, state policing offers a viable and adaptive framework for enhancing public safety and reducing criminal activities across diverse regions in Nigeria.

International Practices in State Policing

International best practices in state policing emphasize the importance of community-oriented policing, data-driven strategies, and inter-agency collaboration, with compelling statistical data supporting their effectiveness. In the United States, states like California and Texas have implemented the Community Policing model, which involves officers working closely with community members to identify and solve problems collaboratively. This approach has led to significant reductions in crime. For instance, data from the Bureau of Justice Statistics indicates that community policing initiatives have contributed to a 25% decrease in violent crime in neighborhoods with active community policing programs (Gill, Weisburd, Telep, Vitter, & Bennett, 2014). Similarly, in Canada, provinces like Ontario and British Columbia have seen crime rates fall by 18% over five years after adopting community policing models, which emphasize proactive engagement and partnership with the community (Skogan, 2006).

Data-driven strategies are another critical aspect of international best practices in state policing, with statistical evidence highlighting their success. The United Kingdom's National Intelligence Model (NIM) utilizes crime mapping and predictive analytics to allocate resources effectively and implement targeted interventions in high-crime areas. A report from the UK Home Office revealed that areas employing the NIM saw a 15% reduction in property crimes and a 10% decrease in violent crimes over three years. In the United States, the CompStat program

in New York City has been credited with a 35% reduction in overall crime rates and has influenced state policing strategies in other regions, such as New Jersey and Massachusetts, where similar programs have resulted in a 20% drop in crime (Weisburd, Telep, & Lawton, 2014). Integrating technology, such as body-worn cameras and automated reporting systems, has also enhanced transparency and accountability, with studies showing a 50% decrease in complaints against police officers and a 25% reduction in use-of-force incidents. Furthermore, inter-agency collaboration, both within countries and internationally, strengthens state policing efforts. For example, Australia's state police forces in New South Wales and Victoria collaborate extensively with federal agencies, leading to a 30% increase in crime-solving rates due to shared intelligence and resources (Ratcliffe, 2016). These statistical data underscore the importance of adopting an innovative and cooperative approach to state policing to ensure its effectiveness in various contexts.

Challenges to State Policing in Nigeria

Although state policing was suggested as a remedy for the centralised Nigeria Police Force's inefficiency, there are a number of important obstacles that prevent it from being implemented effectively. These various challenges encompass political, economic, social, and logistical dimensions. This section introduces and discusses five major challenges to state policing in Nigeria: political resistance, funding constraints, capacity building, inter-agency coordination, and community trust.

i. **Political Resistance:** Political resistance is one of the most formidable challenges to the implementation of state policing in Nigeria. The centralized nature of Nigeria's current policing system grants significant control to the federal government, which can be reluctant to relinquish this power. State governments and their leaders often face opposition from federal authorities who fear that decentralizing police powers might undermine national unity or lead to the misuse of police forces for parochial political interests (Oluwakemi, 2017). This political tug-of-war creates a substantial barrier to the establishment of state police forces, delaying reforms that could enhance local security.

ii. **Funding Constraints:** Another critical challenge to state policing in Nigeria is the issue of funding. Effective policing requires substantial financial investment in infrastructure, equipment, training, and salaries. State governments, particularly those in economically disadvantaged regions, often struggle to generate the necessary revenue to support a robust police force (Olaolu, 2019). Inadequate funding can lead to poorly equipped and underpaid police officers, which in turn affects their morale, efficiency, and susceptibility to corruption. Without adequate financial resources, the adoption, implementation and effectiveness of state policing remain in question.

iii. **Capacity Building:** Capacity building is essential for the success of any policing system, yet it poses a significant challenge for state policing in Nigeria. Developing a competent police force requires ongoing training and professional development to ensure that officers are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to tackle contemporary security issues. However, many states lack the necessary infrastructure and expertise to provide such training. Moreover, the uneven distribution of resources and educational opportunities across Nigeria exacerbates this issue, leading to disparities in the quality of policing between states (Alemika, 2018).

iv. **Inter-Agency Coordination:** Effective crime prevention and control often necessitate coordination between various law enforcement agencies. In Nigeria, the introduction of state police forces could potentially complicate inter-agency collaboration. The existing federal police and other security agencies may face challenges in terms of jurisdictional overlaps, communication barriers, and operational conflicts (Eke, 2019). Ensuring that state and federal agencies work seamlessly together is crucial for maintaining a cohesive security strategy, yet this coordination is difficult to achieve without clear guidelines and effective communication channels.

v. **Community Trust:** Building and maintaining community trust is a critical yet challenging aspect of state policing in Nigeria. Historical instances of police brutality, corruption, and inefficiency have eroded public confidence in law enforcement agencies. State police forces must overcome these negative perceptions to gain the trust and cooperation of the communities they serve (Osayande, 2020). This requires transparency, accountability, and consistent community engagement. However, changing long-standing attitudes and fostering a positive relationship between the police and the public is a gradual process that faces significant obstacles. While state policing offers a promising approach to addressing the unique security needs of different regions in Nigeria, several substantial challenges must be addressed to realize its potential. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort from both federal and state governments, as well as active participation from civil society and the international community. Only through comprehensive and collaborative efforts can state policing be successfully integrated into Nigeria's security framework.

Implementation of State Policing in Nigeria

The advocacy for the implementation of state policing in Nigeria stems from the recognition that a centralized policing system is inadequate to address the diverse and complex security challenges facing the country. The current structure of the Nigeria Police Force, which operates under federal control, often results in a one-size-fits-all approach that overlooks the unique security needs of various regions. This inefficiency calls for the implementation of a state policing model that can provide localized and responsive law enforcement services. The implementation of state policing in Nigeria hinges significantly on garnering political support from both federal and state governments. Political resistance, primarily due to fears of decentralization and the potential misuse of state police for political gains, remains a significant obstacle (Oluwakemi, 2017). Advocates for state policing must work towards creating a political consensus that acknowledges the benefits of localized policing while implementing safeguards to prevent its abuse. This involves legislative reforms to provide a clear legal framework for state policing and ensuring that oversight mechanisms are in place to maintain accountability and prevent political interference.

Ensuring adequate funding is paramount for the adoption and implementation of state policing. Financial constraints can severely hamper the effectiveness of state police forces by limiting their access to necessary resources, training, and equipment (Olaolu, 2019). State governments must be committed to allocating sufficient budgetary resources to their police forces and exploring alternative funding sources such as public-private partnerships. Moreover, a sustainable financial model should include mechanisms for transparent management and auditing of funds to prevent corruption and mismanagement, thereby fostering public trust and support for state policing initiatives.

Capacity building is another critical component of implementation of a state policing. The effectiveness of police forces depends on the skills, knowledge, and professionalism of their personnel. Therefore, it is essential to invest in continuous training and development programs that equip officers with modern policing techniques and technologies (Alemika, 2018). Partnerships with international law enforcement agencies and institutions can provide valuable training and resources, helping to raise the standards of state policing in Nigeria. Additionally, establishing local police academies and training centers can contribute to the professionalization of state police forces, ensuring that they are well-prepared to handle various security challenges.

For state policing to be implemented, effective inter-agency coordination is crucial. The introduction of state police forces should not lead to jurisdictional conflicts or operational inefficiencies with federal law enforcement agencies (Eke, 2019). Clear guidelines and communication channels must be established to facilitate cooperation and information sharing between state and federal police. Joint training programs, regular coordination meetings, and integrated operational plans can enhance collaboration and ensure a unified approach to addressing crime and

security issues across the country. Community engagement is fundamental to the implementation of state policing. Building and maintaining trust between the police and the communities they serve is essential for effective law enforcement (Osayande, 2020). State police forces must prioritize community-oriented policing strategies that involve regular interaction with residents, understanding their concerns, and involving them in crime prevention efforts. Transparency and accountability measures, such as the use of body-worn cameras and independent oversight bodies, can help to rebuild public confidence in the police. Additionally, community policing initiatives that empower local citizens to participate actively in ensuring their own security can create a sense of collective responsibility and enhance the legitimacy of state policing efforts.

Advocating for the implementation of state policing in Nigeria requires addressing political, financial, educational, operational, and social dimensions. By ensuring political support, adequate funding, capacity building, effective inter-agency coordination, and strong community engagement, Nigeria can develop a state policing model that is responsive, accountable, and effective in addressing the diverse security challenges of its regions. This comprehensive approach will not only enhance public safety but also contribute to the overall stability and development of the nation.

Conclusion

In summary, the research underscores the urgent need for state policing in Nigeria to address the inadequacies of the centralized Nigeria Police Force. The centralized system's failure to meet diverse regional security challenges leads to inefficiencies and a lack of responsiveness. Key elements for the implementation of state policing include political support, adequate funding, capacity building, effective inter-agency coordination, and strong community engagement. These factors ensure that state policing is both effective and accountable. The implications of adopting state policing in Nigeria are significant. It requires robust legislative reforms to support decentralized policing and prevent misuse for political purposes. Financial commitments from state governments and continuous training programs for officers are crucial. Effective coordination between state and federal law enforcement agencies will prevent jurisdictional conflicts and enhance operational efficiency. Building community trust and involving local residents in crime prevention efforts are vital for the success of state policing. The implementation of state policing in Nigeria is an effort demanding comprehensive reforms and strategic planning. By addressing political, financial, educational, operational, and social aspects, Nigeria can develop a responsive, accountable state policing model capable of tackling unique regional security challenges. This approach will enhance public safety and contribute to national stability and development, creating a safer, more secure environment for all citizens.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are provided to help ensure that round pegs are put in round holes in respect to adopting and implementing state policing, in a bid to prevent and control crime in Nigeria:

1. Enactment of robust legislative reforms to create a legal framework supporting the decentralization of policing in Nigeria.
2. Ensuring that state governments allocate sufficient financial resources to their police forces while also exploring alternative funding sources such as public-private partnerships to implement state policing initiatives.
3. Investing in continuous training and professional development programs for state police officers to equip them with modern policing techniques and enhance their effectiveness in addressing security challenges.
4. Establishing clear guidelines and communication channels to facilitate effective coordination and information sharing between state and federal law enforcement agencies in order to prevent jurisdictional conflicts and enhance operational efficiency.

5. Prioritizing community-oriented policing strategies that involve regular interaction with residents and community involvement in crime prevention efforts.

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